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D7.5 Sustainability Plan

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronyms/Abbreviations	Definition
CCN	Country Correspondent Network
CCN-RPO study	Country Correspondent Network Research Performing Organisations study
CCN-RFO study	Country Correspondent Network Research Funding Organisations study
CMS	Content Management System
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ETER	European Tertiary Education Register
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interpretable Replicable
ISP	International Satellite Partner
M&E	Monitoring & Evaluation
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
OSAF	Open Science Assessment Framework
OSF	Open Science Framework
RESU	SUPER MoRRI researcher Survey
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
R&I	Research & Innovation
SAT	Self-Assessment Tool
SRTT	Societal Readiness Thinking Tool
SwafS	Science with and for Society

Executive Summary

This report describes the approach to maintain methods, results, and assets from the SUPER MoRRI project. There is a diversity of goals and tasks that together comprise the rationale and execution of SUPER MoRRI. The commitment to provide robust data and information for the monitoring framework and to present all the outputs as responsibly as possible resulted in three main lines of activity: Data collection; Case studies; and Development of an online portal named 'Platform for the Support of Responsibility and Openness and their Monitoring in Innovation and Science Ecosystems' (PROMISE, www.promise4era.eu).

This deliverable D7.5 identifies outputs to be maintained and to open up the results of the data vehicles to other users. The SUPER MoRRI outputs were developed with the potential users in mind. Sustainability in SUPER MoRRI thus is dependent on how potential users do use the SUPER MoRRI results. Since SUPPER MoRRI cannot approach every individual RPO or RFO, the focus has been on existing, European-wide overarching organisations and policy developments, where individual RPO's and RFO's may find inspiration. If these pick up the SUPER MoRRI principles and approaches, this can ensure sustainable use of SUPER MoRRI. For this to happen, it is critical that the PROMISE portal will have a sustained after-life. These organisations and their activities related to M&E are: UNESCO, EOSC, CoARA and the ERA/OECD Monitoring.

Further liaison has been commenced with the Horizon Europe funded project REINFORCING, as a potential interested curator and re-user of SUPER MoRRI data assets. Other relevant Horizon Europe projects that focus on open and responsible R&I practices are GraspOS and OPUS. The relevance of these projects and organisations lies on the one hand in taking custodianship of the PROMISE portal, and on the other hand in the Monitoring and Evaluation frameworks under development by these organisations and projects where insights and outputs of SUPER MoRRI may be of help.

The Recommendations as presented in policy brief No.1 aim to promote responsible research and innovation practices and it's monitoring globally, and as such carry on the SUPER MoRRI knowledge for the future. If the SUPER MoRRI data collection were to be repeated, which we strongly recommend, the relevant activities are described in detail.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Scope and Objective of the Deliverable

The objective of this report is to provide a document that describes the approach to maintain methods, results, and assets from the SUPER MoRRI project. There is a diversity of goals and tasks that together comprise the rationale and execution of SUPER MoRRI. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) as a policy goal aimed to make a more just, inclusive, reflective, open, and responsive research and innovation (R&I) system. From the outset of the SUPER MoRRI journey, a key question was how to monitor and evaluate (M&E) RRI in a responsible way? And in this report, the additional question is not only how to preserve but also carry on the findings into the future.

The measurement of RRI – even independent of which exact understanding of RRI applies – was seen in its complex context and hence the implication was that indicators will be influenced by their use and the purpose for which they are developed. This is an important preamble because SUPER MoRRI had the ambition to generate an understanding that can serve to improve governance of research and innovation: 1) to apply as self-governance (to be performed within institutions and networks conducting research and innovation) and 2) as external governance (performed by research funding organisations, regulatory authorities, and ultimately civil society).

The commitment to provide robust data and information for the monitoring framework and to present all the outputs as responsibly as possible resulted in three main lines of activity:

1. Data collection vehicles to improve indicators originating from “MoRRI” and develop a monitoring framework.
2. In-depth research case studies to deepen our understanding, and
3. Development of an online portal named ‘Platform for the Support of Responsibility and Openness and their Monitoring in Innovation and Science Ecosystems’ (PROMISE, www.promise4era.eu).

For RRI, the project has focused on ‘markers of responsibility’ as general categorization. These are formulated as: Ethics and Integrity; (Gender) Equality, Public Engagement, Open Science and Third Mission which refers to the third academic task of universities (in addition to research and education) relating to entrepreneurship and knowledge transfer.

1.2. Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables

The D7.5 Sustainability report relates directly to D1.3, the Revised Strategic Development Plan for the Monitoring Framework for Responsible Research and Innovation (D1.3). It further builds upon the Implementation plan Monitoring (D2.1), the First, Second and Third Responsible Research and Innovation Monitoring Reports (D2.2, D2.3, D2.5) and the Annotated Methodological Procedures Report (D2.4) which report on the indicator fiches, data sources and procedures. Also, the SUPER MoRRI Dashboard (WP3 Task 3.4), and Designing the RRI self-assessment tool (D6.3) are relevant for this deliverable. Finally, this deliverable also draws on the Policy brief no.1, prepared by WP4.

1.3. Deliverable structure

This Sustainability report is structured as follows: The Executive Summary briefly presents the purpose and contents of this report. Chapter 1 introduces the scope and objectives of the deliverable, its relation to other tasks within the project, and its structure.

Chapter 2 first summarises the approach to develop the content of the sustainability plan. It then goes on to integrate and cluster the SUPER MoRRI outcomes to be preserved including per WP how assets of SUPER MORRI can be sustained, and at what (roughly estimated) costs. Chapter 3 is divided into five sub-sections with each presenting strategies and avenues for sustainability. Chapter 4 presents the cross-cutting recommendations to secure the SUPER MoRRI legacy, followed by a selection of concrete actions.

2. SUPER MoRRI Assets

2.1. Approach

The approach to arrive at this sustainability plan started at the Consortium Meeting in Barcelona (October 2022). Here the consortium collectively reflected on sustainability and discussed what the main assets of SUPER MoRRI would be. It was agreed to contact representatives of the European Commission to inquire where and how they would like to connect the (RRI) monitoring framework to the current European activities regarding open science or the European research area. This took place in January 2023. The suggestions were discussed in detail at the next consortium meeting in Bergen (March 2023). In the course of 2023, WP leaders were invited to present their WP's main assets to preserve SUPER MoRRI's legacy. And during the final event (December 2023), a world café was organised with RRI experts and potential users of SUPER MoRRI to further discuss their needs and issues.

2.2. SUPER MoRRI Assets general

This section provides details on the SUPER MoRRI's data collection vehicles.

The methodological procedures for three large data collection exercises conducted in Work Package 2 of SUPER MoRRI are described in the four consecutive deliverables: D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4. These four describe the Implementation plan (2.1), the First and Second Monitoring report (D2.2 and D2.3), and the the Annotated Methodological Procedures Report (D2.4). These three data collection exercises were the Country Correspondent Network Research Performing Organisations (CCN-RPO) Study, the Country Correspondent Network Research Funding Organisations (CCN-RFO) Study, and the Research Survey (RESU). The secondary data that are used in SUPER MoRRI is described in detail in D2.2 and D2.3, the First and Second Responsible Research and Innovation Monitoring Reports. It is derived from the following external open sources: SheFigures, Eurostat, Eurobarometer, Web of Science/Unpaywall, and the ETER database. Indicator fiches and their sources are available in both reports.

All activities in SUPER MoRRI have been conducted with attention to open science practices. A dedicated project was established on Open Science Framework (OSF) for SUPER MoRRI, with all process and methods documents uploaded as publicly discoverable objects. For each of the CCN-RPO, CCN-RFO and RESU studies a detailed project Protocol was produced and uploaded to OSF (<https://osf.io/z95gw/>). These Protocols contained full explanations of the research approach, methodology and process. Data generated by all SUPER MoRRI studies is stored securely on Fraunhofer OwnCloud as per the project Data Management Plan.

Raw data is currently stored at the Fraunhofer OwnCloud platform. The SUPER MoRRI Data Management Plan (DMP, D8.2) plans for all data sets to be preserved in the research data infrastructure "Fordatis" of the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft (see <https://www.openaccess.fraunhofer.de/en/open-access-strategy.html>). The data will be enriched with significant, standardised metadata and identifiers (DOI). DOIs will also serve to link the data to the corresponding publication data in the Fraunhofer Publica (<http://publica.fraunhofer.de>). A consistent naming protocol for all data files and folders is specified in the updated DMP and will be adhered to rigorously.

SUPER MoRRI is part of the European Commission's Open Data Pilot. As such, Section 2 of the SUPER MoRRI DMP describes plans for making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

The volume of data to store is unlikely to exceed 20 gigabytes. It will definitely not reach a threshold of 2 terabytes at which consideration of additional costs and space for storage would be needed.

The information provided in this Deliverable aims to not duplicate information already publicly available in the deliverables mentioned and in individual studies' Protocols, which are stored at Open Science Framework and will be deposited at Zenodo.

SUPER MoRRI data will be prepared for transmission to WP3 (Dashboard and visualisation) as part of Task 2.6. These data will be prepared in a variety of formats tailored to the monitoring portal, including the indicator dashboard, and to the specific types of data visualisations being used.

In addition to their value as standalone sources for monitoring elements for SUPER MoRRI, these primary data collections discussed in this document were also designed to provide inputs to some of the specific case studies carried out in WP5. The Public Value Research Careers study from WP5 utilised primary data from the Researcher Survey and the CCN-RPO study. The organizational policies and support structures and researchers' public engagement practices" case used primary data from the Researcher Survey combined with data from the CCN RPO study.

2.3. SUPER MoRRI assets per WP

Work package 1 – Critical inspection and strategic planning

WP1 mainly consisted of critical consultation, scoping and assessment of metrics and monitoring practices, resulting in the Revised Strategic Development Plan for the Monitoring Framework for Responsible Research and Innovation (D1.3). D1.3 builds upon the full project time presenting the future aspects of the monitoring framework, and as such this report is the translation into concrete suggestions.

The critical elements to maintain in future monitoring are:

- Maintain a diversified approach to monitoring: do not regress to national level horserace.
- Maintain a reflexive focus on the credible contextualization of monitoring data and information.
- Maintain a strategy of developing monitoring information and tools with different purposes (learning, community building, formative adaptation, etc.).
- Maintain a strategy of monitoring with the objective to support RRI (monitoring *for* RRI not *of* RRI)

The major output of the SUPER MoRRI project is the PROMISE portal (promise4era.eu). PROMISE (see WP3) contains a range of data and information that are designed to support institutional transformation toward more open and responsible cultures and practices of research and innovation. From a strategic point of view the finalisation of the SUPER MoRRI project has overlapped with the initiation of a Horizon Europe project, REINFORCING (<https://reinforcing.eu/>, 2023-2026), that will take over custodianship of PROMISE and its underlying resources and tools (see chapter 3).

Regardless of future decisions about what aspects of PROMISE might be updated, the experimentation and new research conducted by SUPER MoRRI has produced monitoring elements that are innovative

and insightful for understanding the institutionalisation of open and responsible research and innovation from multiple perspectives. This seems to be a value worth pursuing also to develop future iterations of PROMISE.

Work package 2 – Data collection

WP2 was the main data collection vehicle for primary and secondary data. It developed a rigorous and efficient data collection system capable of implementing quantitative and qualitative data collection at micro-, meso- and macro-level across EU member states and selected additional countries from other parts of the world (D2.1 and D2.4). It delivered basic descriptive monitoring results in designated monitoring reports (D2.2, D2.3 and D2.5) and quality-assured data sets to WP3 (Dashboard and visualisation) for the purposes of user-adjusted, web-based access to results.

The critical elements to maintain in future monitoring are:

- WP2 – Country Correspondents network (CCN) with experts in all EU member states.
- Strong methodological descriptions of all primary data collection allowing future similar data collections available at OSF and in deliverables.
- Primary data collections (RFO study, RPO study, RESU) made available on Zenodo and in useful and interpreted formats on the PROMISE portal.
- Secondary (Eurostat, She-figures, Eurobarometer, OECD, MORE3/More4) made available on Zenodo and in useful and interpreted formats on the PROMISE portal.

Whilst all source material is available as open data at Zenodo, the PROMISE portal contains access to raw data and information alongside pre-formatted selections and visualisations of these data and information resources, as prepared by the SUPER MoRRI team. However, possible exploitations of the available data and information were not exhausted during SUPER MoRRI. This was partly due to Covid-19 interruptions, but also due to the volume of data generated by the various empirical studies conducted. Further indicators, visualisations, and other resources will certainly be possible as part of continuing development of PROMISE. It is anticipated that the handover of PROMISE will be a seamless transition that will quickly allow its new managers to be creative and develop new outputs to further populate and enhance the site.

Big data and language learning model-based tools will no doubt become useful components of future monitoring efforts. However, the SUPER MoRRI experience and the PROMISE portal would suggest that the need for context-sensitive and the value of reflexive approaches to monitoring should not be overlooked in the rush to ‘scrape and dump’ data. A balanced approach to monitoring should maintain a consistent emphasis also on diverse and critical monitoring approaches in order to engage with the multiple challenges involved in supporting institutional change toward more open and responsible cultures and practices in research and innovation.

If the data collection were to be repeated, which we strongly recommend, this will need the following activities:

- Reinstall the Country Correspondent Network, as data collection in local languages is critical to grasp the diversity and intricacies of Member state policies on Open and Responsible R&I practices. If possible, the CCN could be expanded to include more global countries currently not

represented. In the meantime, country correspondents could register as experts with the REINFORCING project.

- A funding body or organisation that will cover the costs of the data collection procedures, handling of the data, coding practices, making data open source available, data transfer and all other related activities. We suggest that a next round of the RPO and RFO's to be conducted around 2025-2026.
- In terms of costs, the budget for a repetition of data collection would be:
 - Country correspondent payments: 27x €5,000 = 135,000€
 - 60 (PM) Person months cost for activities: 60x 8,000€ = 480,000€

Work package 3 – Dashboard and visualisation

WP3 included all the technical and visual aspects of SUPER MoRRI, including identification of functional and non-functional requirements needed to design the ICT architecture, calibration of the proposed dashboards, designing and specification of technical requirements, as well as designing the solution architecture of the PROMISE portal and website.

The critical elements to maintain in future monitoring are:

- Website
- Dashboard
- Self Assessment Tool
- PROMISE Portal

PROMISE provides a heterogeneous range of monitoring elements. These elements range from 'national dashboard' indicators to categorical indicators at organisational level, to narratives of specific qualitative cases. This variety of indicators are suitable for different monitoring purposes. The efforts required to produce these different elements varied quite significantly, as discussed in the Annotated Methodological Procedures Report (D2.4). The feasibility or efficiency of replicating these data generation processes thus also varies considerably.

The next phase of further developing PROMISE is supported by a number of contributory outputs produced by the SUPER MoRRI project of which the research designs and methods used to generate primary data are specified, ensuring future replication of any part of the SUPER MoRRI research programme is feasible. In addition, detailed project Protocols were developed for each of the research studies conducted in SUPER MoRRI, which are publicly available from the project site at Open Science Framework. Together these resources are designed to ensure the continuity of monitoring to support open and responsible research innovation through PROMISE.

In the digital sphere, progress in content management systems (CMS) has been rapid during the lifespan of the SUPER MoRRI project. PROMISE has taken advantage of user-friendly CMS options that are simpler for non-ICT professionals to use. Maintaining and enhancing the look and feel of a contemporary online interface, suitable for versatile forms of data presentation, visualization, and interrogation should be a priority in the future management of PROMISE.

To update and maintain the portal, website, dashboard, and self-assessment tool, it is critical to have a new hosting organization, that takes over custodianship of PROMISE and its underlying resources and tools. If this were to be the REINFORCING project, as suggested under WP1, the sustainability

issues, technical requirement and annual costs for each of the components are presented below in figure 1.

Figure 1 Overview of costs for portal and website maintenance

Component	Sustainability issues	Technical requirements	Man-hours	Annual cost
Website	update of the content, informations presented in the website, links to external sources	php	dependent on the amount of material updated (aprox. 1 h/article)	
Website	Migration on other infrastructure	php, system administrator	1-2 days	
Website	update of the modules and core	php, system administrator	dependent on the amount of material updated - 1-2h/month	
Website	Hosting/ domain		1-2 hours/year	up to 100 euro
PROMISE portal	Update of the content, informations presented in the portal, links to external sources	Wordpress	dependent on the complexity of the material updated (aprox. 1 h/article)	
Dashboard	Update of the indicators	Java, Vaadin , JavaScript (pentru amCharts), SQL	dependent on the amount of material updated (up to 5 days)	
Dashboard	Installation and transfer of app and data/System clone or docker container	Sys admin/DevOps	5-10 days	
Self assessment tool	Update of the SAT form (questions of the survey to be updated)	None. Is done via SAT interface	dependent on the amount of material updated. Up to 1 day for update of entire form	
Self assessment tool	Installation and transfer of app and data/System clone or docker container	Sys admin/DevOps	5-10 days	

In terms of costs, it would be per annum (1000€/day):

- Website: estimated 5 days x €1,000 = 5,000€
- Dashboard: estimated 10 days x €1,000 = 10,000€
- Self-Assessment Tool: 7.5 days x €1,000 = 7,500€
- PROMISE Portal: 50 items in secondary data to update = 50 hours; 6.25 days x €1,000 = 6,250€

Work package 4 – International benchmarking

WP4 aimed to establish a diverse network of stakeholders (International Satellite Partners) from different international locations outside of Europe and ensure their continuous critical involvement as a global sounding board for the research activities in SUPER MoRRI and as providers of non-European data points for comparative purposes. The International Satellite Partners (ISPs) provided these global voices.

The critical elements to maintain in future monitoring are:

- The International Satellite Partners are individuals, and hence their continued commitment after the project ends terminates as well. However, the three ISP's that acted as data collector could register as experts with the REINFORCING project.
- Otherwise, the legacy of the international benchmarking is reflected in the policy brief no.1 and the specific WP4 deliverables that collected all the opinions of the ISPs on RRI monitoring in non-European countries.

In the policy brief the nine policy recommendations aim to promote responsible research and innovation practices and it's monitoring globally, and as such carry on the SUPER MoRRI knowledge for the future.

1. Promote global dialogue by linking European RRI concepts with international principles like open science, sustainability, and frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
2. Involve stakeholders in crafting region-specific indicators, adjusting explanations and engagement strategies to suit their diverse comprehension levels.
3. Highlight the need to contextualize metrics across various levels (regional, national, organizational, individual), and advocate for indicators tailored to these distinctions.
4. Execute proactive data collection, address gaps transparently, and acknowledge missing data to ensure a reliable dataset for evaluations.
5. Highlight the importance of specifying indicators and recognizing limitations to avoid overlooking vital aspects of responsible research and innovation.
6. Advocate for ongoing learning and adaptation in indicator use, refining them based on feedback, experience, and emerging knowledge.
7. Utilize indicators for evidence-based policymaking to develop stable policies supporting responsible research and innovation practices.
8. Encourage funding programs that integrate RRI concepts into evaluation criteria, incentivizing responsible research practices in the community.
9. Back the integration of RRI concepts in PhD training to equip future researchers with responsible research knowledge.

Work package 5 – Scientific, social, economic and democratic benefits

This WP is the core component of the project's innovative research effort. A set of empirical studies investigated how responsible practices in R&I result in scientific, democratic, social and economic benefits. WP5 aimed to clarify pathways from RRI practices and policies to benefits, and their interrelation between different RRI-keys; to investigate and identify patterns of RRI and its benefits using large scale data sets; to synthesize the results and identify markers of responsibility to monitor the benefit of RRI; and to specify benefits of RRI through the Theory of Change approach. To this end six extensive case studies have been carried out. The case studies were presented in a structured way to allow for comparative analysis. As such, the case studies build upon qualitative interview material. These materials are not available for reuse due to GDPR-regulation. From the transcribed materials, analysis was carried out, resulting in six written cases studies based upon anonymized materials. The case studies are presented in deliverables D5.2: Pattern Studies Report and D5.3: Pathway Studies Report. Short texts were derived and tagged from the case studies to be included in the PROMISE portal for contextual information.

The critical elements that will remain are (journal) publications that are based on the case studies; the monitoring and /or the monitoring framework; and the ecosystem activities. The publications will be developed after the end of the project. Otherwise, the blogposts on the SUPER MoRRI website will remain.

Work package 6 – Self-assessment

The overall aim of WP6 was to develop an assessment method that can be of assistance to all types of Research Performing Organisations (RPO's) and revolves around a self-assessment RRI performance tool that aims at measuring the performance of their projects as well as a model to compare with their peers. The self-assessment results in 'RRI readiness levels' and identifies levels of performance from minimum standard to best practice. To achieve each performance step (or level), an organization must

meet a series of assessment criteria which include both quantitative and qualitative measurements. One must achieve level one of each priority or have an action plan in place to ensure they do so within an agreed timescale. Such further development demonstrates growth or functionally increased performance in RRI. An online self-assessment tool (SAT) is developed, where each organization can monitor its performance against RRI markers of responsibility.

The SAT aims to include and focus mainly (but not necessarily exclusively) on indicators with pre-defined scales of measurement, although some open answer questions may still be desirable. While this may involve some loss in terms of flexibility, there are also some gains:

- Because of having pre-defined answers (measured at categorical/nominal, ordinal, interval or ratio scales), the SAT will allow to compute composite indicators and make comparisons:
 - Either within the same project
 - between different time points
 - between reported results and targets
 - Or between one's project and others
 - comparing with other projects within the same organization (with full access to other projects data);
 - comparing with outside projects (who have given their consent for sharing data, but under anonymous use: i.e. comparisons will be made with aggregates of other projects with a minimum number of projects needed in a category before aggregates become accessible).

Whilst there are overlaps between the SAT and the Societal Readiness Thinking Tool SRTT (<https://thinkingtool.eu/>), the SAT is scalable whereas the SRTT is not. The SAT is made available on the PROMISE portal.

The critical elements to maintain for future monitoring are the Self-assessment Tool on the portal. The estimated costs to maintain and update the Tool are already indicated under WP3.

Work package 7 – Impact and communication

The tasks in WP7 were designed with an impact-perspective in mind. Interactions were pursued with the project's stakeholder environment to maximise opportunities for impact from the beginning. The focus on engagement, involvement and co-creation enabled a broad variety of stakeholders to participate in SUPER MoRRI. WP7 operated as an impact manager: A particular impact driven activity has been the monthly gathering of the so-called SwafS Ecosystem, a collection of SwafS-funded RRI projects focusing on gender, citizen science, open science, grounding practices or regional RRI that collectively discussed all aspects of Monitoring and Evaluation of RRI. The internal turning point within the Ecosystem was the realization that the breadth of projects demonstrated such diversity and translational issues (how to adopt RRI in context) that for Monitoring and Evaluation no one-size-fits-all could apply. One of the immediate benefits was that it glued the RRI-project partners and the stakeholders together building a network which co-designed and co-implemented the course of the project. The expertise to do that is a benefit that will be carried on by everyone. Working in transdisciplinary projects, in whatever topic, requires finding the language to bridge the needs, and support open and responsible R&I practices.

The critical elements to maintain in future monitoring are:

- The SwafS Ecosystem RRI experts are individuals, and hence their continued commitment after the project ends terminates as well. However, SwafS Ecosystem partners could register as experts with the REINFORCING project.
- The experts participating in the ecosystem will continue to share and further develop the common knowledge and expertise that will be beneficial to R&I in missions, clusters, and next projects. The REINFORCING aims to install a smaller version of the Ecosystem as a sounding board for their activities. Transfer of names and contact information will be done according to GDPR.

3. Strategies for sustainability

In the second review meeting for the SUPER MoRRI project advice was received that a plan for the sustainability of the major project outputs should be developed. This deliverable D7.5, identified outputs to be maintained in the previous chapter. In this chapter suggestions to maintain and open up the results of the data vehicles to other users are presented.

The SUPER MoRRI outputs were developed with the potential users in mind: what kind of information would be of help for RPO's and RFO's to further their open and responsible practices, both in terms of strategy and activity. That has resulted in the monitoring framework as presented, the markers of responsibility and the portal to have access to information of relevance to users in a responsible way. So, sustainability in SUPER MoRRI thus is dependent on how potential users do use our SUPER MoRRI results. Since SUPPER MoRRI cannot approach every individual RPO or RFO, we have focused on existing, European-wide overarching organisations and policy developments, where individual RPO's and RFO's may find inspiration. If these pick up the SUPER MoRRI principles and approaches, this can ensure sustainable use of SUPER MoRRI. For this to happen, it is critical that the portal, which is only live since the last months of the project, will have a sustained after-life. During the final event of SUPER MoRRI connections to relevant organisations and projects have been made (see below).

As part of this process, liaison has been commenced with the Horizon Europe funded project REINFORCING, as a potential interested curator and re-user of SUPER MoRRI data assets. Other relevant Horizon Europe projects that focus on open and responsible R&I practices are GraspOS and OPUS. Further suggestions include liaising with the ERA monitoring framework as part of ERA Action 19, the UNESCO Open Science Working Group (see <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/implementation>), EOSC future and their monitoring of open science at macro (member state) level (see <https://zenodo.org/communities/eoscobservatory?page=1&size=20>). Finally, it is recommended by the EC open science unit of DGRTD to liaise with the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), which was recently launched (see figure 2).

The relevance of these projects and organisations lies on the one hand in taking custodianship of the PROMISE portal, and on the other hand in the Monitoring and Evaluation frameworks under development by these organisations and projects where insights and outputs of SUPER MoRRI may be of help. This will be described in more detail below.

Figure 2 Overview of organisations and projects

3.1. Horizon Europe Projects

3.1.1 REINFORCING

REINFORCING

Responsible tErritories and Institutions
eNable and Foster Open Research and inClusive
Innovation for traNsition Gobernance

The REINFORCING project (<https://reinforcing.eu/>) was funded by Horizon Europe under the call ERA-01-40 (2022) and consists of three parts:

- The first involves **consolidating the evidence base and develop innovative guidance** and other materials, which can support institutions and territories to implement sustainable institutional changes and open up to society^[2]. It should take into account and build on the learning and knowledge developed by Horizon 2020's Science with and for Society programme^[3] and potentially other sources of knowledge.
- The second part involves **financial support to third parties**, by launching 'cascading grant' call(s) to support institutions and territories from across the ERA to implement sustainable institutional changes towards open and responsible research and innovation.

- The third part involves acting as a **central point of expertise and support services on open and responsible research and innovation** for institutions and projects under Horizon Europe and within the European Research Area. This point of expertise should have appropriate high-level visibility, and the ability to interact and support all parts of the research and innovation system (all parts of quadruple helix, disciplines, sectors). [...]

The action should **evaluate its impacts** and **develop recommendations** useful to policy makers and those responsible for the governance of research and innovation institutions. [...] It should **develop close co-operation with other relevant projects**, with a view to fostering collaboration and the early sharing of knowledge and evidence.

Especially task 1 and 3 and the impact evaluation tie in to SUPER MoRRI results directly.

The green and digital transitions have become an urgency that can no longer wait. The twin transition, as they have come to be known, will bring enormous benefits but also undesired externalities. To address externalities Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) is important. Making the digital and green transitions fair and inclusive is key. To succeed, institutions and territories need to shift to more open and transparent R&I practices in which all actors share responsibility to develop services and products that are acceptable, sustainable and bring social satisfaction. Open and Responsible R&I promotes collaborative efforts and knowledge transfer to help identify such solutions more effectively. From sharing research outputs as early as possible to engaging citizens in co-creation processes and promoting responsible research and innovation, R&I should be open to the whole society.

REINFORCING aims to become the EU Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) central point of knowledge and expertise that supports territories and institutions in implementing ORRI activities. For this task it will start from the RRI-Tools database. And the REINFORCING One-Stop Source platform supplies the EU R&I ecosystem with tools, resources, training and different services to help R&I actors in their ORRI journey.

SUPER MoRRI outputs can both be used as sources of relevant information in the central point of knowledge and expertise, whilst the PROMISE portal could become part of the One-stop-shop. Since the SUPER MoRRI coordinator is also part of REINFORCING, a smooth transition is envisioned.

REINFORCING will also develop a virtual map where one will be able to find peers to help in the ORRI journey. From organizations with experience in implementing ORRI to facilitators who can support third parties in implementing ORRI. This mapping will help institutions connect with local experts, matching their need for specific competences and will be used to provide matchmaking services. Here the SUPER MoRRI country correspondents, Ecosystem RRI experts and interested International Satellite Partners can register as individuals to being available for REINFORCING and ORRI.

3.1.2 GraspOS

The aim of GraspOS (<https://graspos.eu/>) is to support the emerging policy reforms and pave the way towards an Open Science aware Responsible Research Assessment system. The project will develop, assess, and operate an open and trusted federated infrastructure for next generation research metrics and indicators, offering data, tools, services and guidance. Introducing Open Science practices in Responsible Research Assessment is not a trivial task and we cannot simply transpose traditional assessment approaches from current bibliometric, a one-size-fits-all approach, in a straightforward manner to assess research in an emerging open science ecosystem. Even though the primary aim of GraspOS is to develop and operationalize an infrastructure for metrics (data-tools-services), one can expect that this will have an uptake and impact only if it is able to convince on its merits. This means that the infrastructure should be carefully crafted to address specific needs, bring trust, provide practical tools, and be easily embedded in monitoring processes (e.g., via EOSC).

GraspOS Results will be in:

- [Open Science Assessment Framework](#)
- [Assessment Portfolios](#)
- [Assessment Registry](#)
- [Enrichment Services](#)
- [Monitoring Services](#)
- [Open and Federated Research Assessment Infrastructure](#)
- [Pilots](#)
- [Community of Practice](#)
- [Training material](#)

A co-developed Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF) will document and provide options on how indicators and tools used in a particular evaluation setting align with the specific characteristics of the assessment context, such as the disciplinary and institutional context and the level at which the assessment takes place (e.g., individual researchers, research groups, research institutions, national level). It will be a key resource for advising implementation and next steps.

The following diagram (figure 3) gives a high-level view of how OSAF is in the core of GraspOS binding the community with the infrastructure.

Figure 3 Overview of the Open Science Assessment Framework

SUPER MoRRI’s perspective on monitoring, especially credible contextualization and responsible quantification are relevant principles to transfer to GraspOS. A SUPER MoRRI partner will be able to communicate the SUPER MoRRI insights and make sure that duplication of efforts will be avoided. Especially policy commitments and policy interventions at the Research Performing Organisation level and how this is visualized in the PROMISE portal may be an inspiration to this metric driven project.

3.1.3 OPUS

The Open and Universal Science (OPUS) project (<https://opusproject.eu/>) develops coordination and support measures to reform the assessment of research and researchers at Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) towards a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to take up Open Science practices. The OPUS project is an EU-funded project implemented by an eighteen-organisations consortium.

They understand the term ‘Open Science’ to refer to practices providing open access to research outputs, early and open sharing of research, participation in open peer-review, measures to ensure

reproducibility of results, and involving all stakeholders in co-creation. OPUS helps reform the assessment of research(ers), along with the following:

- Conduct a comprehensive [state-of-the-art on existing literature and initiatives for Open Science](#)
- Develop [a comprehensive set of interventions to implement Open Science](#) at RPOs and RFOs
- Develop [realistic indicators and metrics to monitor and drive Open Science](#) at RPOs and RFOs
- Test the interventions and indicators and metrics via action plans in pilots at RPOs and RFOs
- Utilise a stakeholder-driven feedback loop to develop, monitor, refine, and validate actions
- Synthesise outcomes into [policy briefs](#) and a revised OS-CAM2 for research(er) assessment

OPUS will develop a set of interventions for Open Science toward a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to take up practices of providing open access to research outputs, early and open sharing of research, participation in open peer-review, measures to ensure reproducibility of results, and involving all stakeholders in co-creation.

SUPER MoRRI has no partner overlap with OPUS. And their focus on Open Science is narrower than what we would understand as Open and Responsible R&I practices. However, OPUS specifically addresses RPO's and RFO's which were the prime target of SUPER MORRI too, and a number of their partners represent researchers from all over Europe (Eurodoc, ICORSA, Marie Curie Alumni Association) who could benefit from the SUPER MoRRI outputs, specifically those from the Researcher Survey.

3.2. CoARA

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA, <https://coara.eu/>) was initiated by the joint support of Science Europe, the European University Association (EUA), and the European Commission. The secretariat is based at the European Science Foundation in Strasbourg. The process of drafting an Agreement on reforming research assessment was initiated in January 2022. More than 350 organisations from over 40 countries were involved. Organisations involved included funders, universities, research centres, institutes and infrastructures, associations and alliances, national and regional authorities, etc representing a broad diversity of views and perspectives. The signatories will work together **to enable systemic reform** on the basis of common principles within an agreed timeframe, and to facilitate exchanges of information and mutual learning between all those willing to improve research assessment practices.

The vision of CoARA is that the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators. The Agreement of the Coalition, based on ten commitments, establishes a common direction for research assessment reform, while respecting organisations' autonomy. Some of the commitments are relevant to SUPER MoRRI, these include among others:

1. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.
2. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools, and processes.
3. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.
4. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.
5. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of the-art in research on research and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment sets a shared direction for changes in assessment practices for research, researchers and research performing organisations, with the overarching goal to maximise the quality and impact of research. There are several working groups that focus on e.g. open research infrastructures, responsible metrics and indicators, multilingualism and bias, experiments in assessment, careers etc.

Questions that CoARA needs to address where results of the SUPER MoRRI Researcher survey, and the observed practices can be of support are e.g.:

- How can we move from research assessment to academic career assessment?
- How can we include a diversity of transversal skills in the assessment?
- What prevents RPOs of appropriately crediting RRI practices?
- What skills are of particular interest to support innovation?
- How to convince RPO leadership of the strategic importance of RRI, and why should they care?
- How to convince administrators and managers to change operationally?

SUPER MoRRI can provide answers to (some of) these questions and can underpin the answers with the outputs and visualisations at the PROMISE portal.

3.3. ERA/OECD Monitoring Framework

The European Research Area (ERA) is the ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU. It helps countries be more effective together, by strongly aligning their research policies and programmes. The free circulation of researchers and knowledge enables better cross-border cooperation, building of critical mass and continent-wide competition. ERA was launched in 2000 and a process to revitalise it began in 2018.

The European Research Area Policy Agenda for the period 2022-2024 presents an overview of actions. Action number 19, to establish an efficient and effective ERA Monitoring Mechanism, will review and update the ERA monitoring system to better capture progress made towards the individual ERA priorities and inform evidence-based policy-making in the ERA. Elements of the new monitoring will be:

- (1) the ERA Scoreboard/Dashboard, including indicators on the progress towards ERA;
- (2) an online policy platform to share qualitative information on strategies and initiatives;
- (3) regular policy dialogues between Member States and the Commission to share best practices and as a mutual learning exercise;

(4) reporting on each Member State, which will feed into the policy dialogues, as well as a mid-term review on the implementation of the ERA policy agenda.

In a Note (<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9578-2022-INIT/en/pdf>) the European Commission instigated on the “State of play of the implementation of the new governance of the ERA”, and as such established a new ERA Forum (in the form of a Commission expert group). In an Annex to the Note

- (4) The new ERA monitoring mechanism should collect and analyse both quantitative and qualitative information regarding the progress in contributing to the ERA priority areas and in implementing the actions of the ERA Policy Agenda.
- (5) Progress should be monitored along the 16 priority areas for joint action (ERA priorities) as set out in the Pact for R&I
- (6) The ERA monitoring mechanism will be set up in such a way as to avoid additional administrative burden, and therefore will use existing indicators and available data (e.g. Eurostat, OECD)
- (8) The online ERA policy platform will be a user-friendly platform for informing on (i) the implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda at Union and national level and on (ii) other relevant investments, reforms and activities supporting the principles and ERA priority areas
- (12) As a minimum requirement, **the platform** will be composed of the following sections:
 - Visualised data, e.g. displaying the scoreboard, dashboard (by country; by priority/by action), investments;
 - Data portal enabling up- or downloading of data/information used by the scoreboard and the dashboard and data/information e.g. on policies, reforms, investments;
 - Information portal for access to the descriptions of ERA Policy Agenda actions, other ERA-related documents and all reports.
- (14) In line with the Pact for R&I, **the scoreboard** monitors progress towards the ERA objectives at Union level”. It “should assess the overall consolidation and collective progress of ERA priorities and should only display aggregated data at EU level”.
- (15) The scoreboard will show the overall progress on the priority areas for joint action at EU level based on a limited number of quantitative indicators.
- (16) The indicators would consist mainly of outcome and impact indicators.
- (17) The number of indicators per priority area does not need to be the same, however, a balance of indicators should be aimed for.

Acknowledging that EC policy activities take shape collectively with policy makers in a Member States, it will be difficult to raise sufficient attention for SUPER MoRRI outputs and the PROMISE portal. Nevertheless, some of the requirements and plans above on the ERA monitoring (which most likely will be hosted by the OECD), align perfectly with the SUPER MoRRI results. Specifically, it would be good if the SUPER MoRRI principles of credible contextualization and responsible quantification would be adopted and or endorsed. The routes or way to do that is, as SUPER MoRRI, to hand over to the European Commission, and ask them to carry on SUPER MoRRI’s legacy to the ERA Monitoring.

3.4. UNESCO Open Science

Open science has the potential of making the scientific process more transparent, inclusive and democratic. It increases scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society; makes multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone; and opens the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.

Our interconnected world needs open science to help solve complex social, environmental, and economic challenges and achieve the Sustainable Development Goals. By promoting science that is more accessible, inclusive and transparent, open science furthers the right of everyone to share in scientific advancement and its benefits as stated in Article 27.1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (adopted in 2021, <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>) provides an internationally agreed definition, as well as a set of shared values and guiding principles for open science. It also identifies a set of actions conducive to a fair and equitable operationalization of open science for all at the individual, institutional, national, regional and international levels. The broad definition of open science not only includes ‘open scientific knowledge’ and ‘open science infrastructures’ but also ‘open dialogue with other knowledge systems’ and ‘open engagement of societal actors’ (see figure 4).

Figure 4 Illustration of the areas of concerns mobilised by the UNESCO recommendation on Open Science (left). Illustration of the values and principles mobilised by the UNESCO recommendation on Open Science (right). Source: UNESCO (2021).

Values include Quality and integrity; Collective benefit recognizing that science is a global public good that belongs to all of humanity; Equity and fairness; Diversity and inclusiveness embracing diversity of knowledge, practices, workflows, languages and research topics and outputs.

Guiding principles include Transparency, scrutiny, critique and reproducibility; Equality of opportunities; Responsibility, respect and accountability; Collaboration, participation and inclusion; Flexibility to acknowledge that there is no one-size-fits-all; and Sustainability to be as efficient and impactful as possible by building on long-term practices, services, infrastructures and funding models to ensure participation of scientists from less-privileged countries or institutions.

Specific Working groups are preparing for the implementation of the Recommendation. Recently, a UNESCO OPEN SCIENCE OUTLOOK 2023 - Status and Trends Around the World was launched. The Outlook aims to review the status and trends in open science at global, regional and national levels, in part to facilitate monitoring the progress for the implementation of the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science and to support Member States to initiate actions by collecting and sharing innovative practices in open science.

SUPER MoRRI outputs speak particularly to the open engagement of societal actors and to open dialogue with other knowledge systems. Also, the values and principles of UNESCO's open science align well with Open and Responsible practices as experienced by SUPER MoRRI. The fact that SUPER MORRI had a global benchmarking activity will help to direct the focus beyond the European context. This will help to address the following questions:

- What should we take or leave for M&E at global level from Europe?
- How to capture the diversity of open science practices
- How can the lessons learned from SUPER MoRRI be integrated into the global monitoring of Open Science, with a particular focus on promoting equity and capturing the diversity of science landscapes worldwide?

3.5. EOSC Future

EOSC Future is an EU-funded H2020 project that is implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). EOSC will give European researchers access to a wide web of FAIR data and related services. The EOSC Observatory is a policy intelligence tool being developed by the EOSC Future project for monitoring policies, practices, and impacts related to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It will support the EOSC community in tracking the implementation of EOSC and the policy makers in developing actionable policies. To this end, the [EOSC Observatory | Zenodo](#) provides a series of documents on monitoring and evaluation of open science practices, such as:

- EOSC Catalogue of best practices (January 2023)
- Survey on national contributions to EOSC 2022
- Data on national contributions to EOSC 2022
- Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC
- Introduction to EOSC Observatory: The EOSC Observatory is a policy intelligence tool for monitoring policies, practices, and impacts related to EOSC and Open Science at national and institutional levels in Europe. The EOSC Observatory has been developed by OpenAIRE and Technopolis Group.

In figure 5 the Monitoring Framework is described in more detail.

Figure 5 The EOSC Monitoring Framework

1 Executive Summary

The Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC consists of three monitoring dimensions and eight categories that are relevant for EOSC and forms a matrix for the specific indicators as in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: Monitoring Matrix for National Contributions to EOSC

	Policies	Practices	Impact
Publications	Indicators	Indicators	Indicators
Data			
Software			
Services			
Infrastructure			
Skills/Training			
Assessment			
Engagement			

The monitoring framework essentially consists of sets of indicators to track the implementation of EOSC across the policies, practices, and impacts identified for each of the eight categories relevant for EOSC. There are currently only indicators proposed for policies and practices (with none yet for impact) as in Table 1-2.

Table 1-2: Types of Indicators for National Contributions to EOSC

	Policies	Practices
Publications	Countries with a National Policy	Countries with National Monitoring
Data		
Software	Countries with a Financial Strategy	Countries with Use Cases
Services		
Infrastructure	Country RPOs with a Policy	Country Investments
Skills/Training	Country RFOs with a Policy	Country Outputs
Assessment		
Engagement		

The monitoring framework currently consists of 48 indicators for policies and 48 indicators for practices. The indicators will be integrated into a new revised survey on National Contributions to EOSC that will be targeted at Member States and Associated Countries in the EOSC Steering Board and will run annually from 2022. The indicators will be iteratively tested in the annual surveys and will be adjusted where necessary from feedback.

The data collected from the annual surveys will be openly published every year in the interactive online dashboard of the EOSC Observatory and will enable the EOSC Steering Board and EOSC community to track the EOSC readiness of the countries and support the countries in setting and aligning their EOSC targets, developing actionable policies for EOSC, and sharing EOSC use cases with each other for mutual learning.

The rationale for the framework is that the indicators that were originally listed, and for which there are data provided by Member states remain. It means that more qualitative, narratives run the risk of getting discarded. From a SUPER MoRRI perspective, it is these types of indicators that would cover the engagement, dialogue and other knowledge system interactions (cf. the UNESCO definition) disappear. The indicators for the 'Engagement' category currently only refer to citizen science:

- Share of countries with a national policy on Citizen Science
- Share of countries with a Financial Strategy on Citizen Science
- Share of country RPO's with a policy on citizen science
- Share of country RFO's with a policy on citizen science

Especially as regards the latter two, SUPER MoRRI is able to provide contextualized information on citizen science also in relation to public engagement and open science policies. Again, in this particular case the EC may be able to transfer the message on SUPER MoRRI insights. The EOOSC has substantial budget and may be able to repeat the RPO and RFO studies as performed by SUPER MoRRI in a later stage.

4. Recommendations for Sustainability

SUPER MoRRI's policy brief No.1 presents nine policy recommendations that aim to promote responsible research and innovation practices and it's monitoring globally, and as such carry on the SUPER MoRRI knowledge for the future. These are based upon SUPER MoRRI's guiding principles.

1. Promote global dialogue by linking European RRI concepts with international principles like open science, sustainability, and frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
2. Involve stakeholders in crafting region-specific indicators, adjusting explanations and engagement strategies to suit their diverse comprehension levels.
3. Highlight the need to contextualize metrics across various levels (regional, national, organizational, individual), and advocate for indicators tailored to these distinctions.
4. Execute proactive data collection, address gaps transparently, and acknowledge missing data to ensure a reliable dataset for evaluations.
5. Highlight the importance of specifying indicators and recognizing limitations to avoid overlooking vital aspects of responsible research and innovation.
6. Advocate for ongoing learning and adaptation in indicator use, refining them based on feedback, experience, and emerging knowledge.
7. Utilize indicators for evidence-based policymaking to develop stable policies supporting responsible research and innovation practices.
8. Encourage funding programs that integrate RRI concepts into evaluation criteria, incentivizing responsible research practices in the community.
9. Back the integration of RRI concepts in PhD training to equip future researchers with responsible research knowledge.

If the SUPER MoRRI data collection were to be repeated, which we strongly recommend, this will need the following activities:

- Reinstall the Country Correspondent Network, as data collection in local languages is critical to grasp the diversity and intricacies of Member state policies on Open and Responsible R&I practices and expand the number of countries. In the meantime, country correspondents could register as experts with the REINFORCING project.
- A funding body or organisation that will cover the costs of the data collection procedures, handling of the data, coding practices, making data open source available, data transfer and all other related activities. We suggest that a next round of the RPO and RFO's to be conducted around 2025-2026.
- We recommend maintaining the critical elements for future monitoring that are presented in the Dashboard, the Self Assessment Tool, and the PROMISE Portal. This will be hosted for the next two years by a temporary project, REINFORCING. We recommend further to use this time for sustained landing in a non-temporary organisation connected to RPO's or RFO's or (global) research assessment bodies.

In view of the sustained use of SUPER MoRRI's results, the following recommendations to the European Commission were formulated:

- Endorse, communicate and distribute SUPER MoRRI's documents and deliverables on monitoring, principles and markers of responsibility to the European Alliances, to the European University Association, Science Europe and their member state partners, European and global organisations active in relation to research assessment and open science such as CoARA, the ERA/OECD Monitoring, EOSC and UNESCO's Recommendations on Science. We recommend the DGRTD unit of Open science, to actively follow up on this to highlight the relevance of this project to the users.
- Endorse, communicate and distribute potential users to the PROMISE portal and the data through the applicants for Horizon Europe funding, by including it in the work programmes. the relevant documents to (Recommendation on Open Science and the Recommendation on Science and Scientific Research 2017).
- Make sure to continuously integrate the SwafS Ecosystem RRI experts in all phases of Horizon Europe funding, and hence their continued commitment after the project ends. It is critical to build upon the experts to share and further develop the common knowledge and expertise that will be beneficial to R&I in missions, clusters, and next projects.

SUPER MoRRI

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